

THREE DIMENSIONAL WOVEN GLASS FABRICS AS REINFORCEMENTS IN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A three dimensional woven glass fabric is produced on velvet weaving machines with glass yarns. It is an integrally woven sandwich fabric, with which it is easy to produce a sandwich laminate for all kinds of composite products. The strength of the vertical fibres makes, that also after impregnation with a resin matrix the sandwich structure is maintained. The result is a laminate with high strength and stiffness and low weight. On each side of this sandwich laminate additional reinforcement materials can be laminated to establish the mechanical properties of a finished product.

GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED PRODUCTS ARE currently a building up of separate layers of reinforcement materials impregnated with a resin matrix. To reduce the weight of these so called full laminates, all kinds of core materials are available on the market. All these materials, such as non wovens, wood, foams, honeycomb, etc., have one thing in common. The bonding to the reinforcement layers must always be achieved in a chemical way and is often not so easy to produce.

By weaving the vertical glass fibres into the upper and lower

lower plain woven fabrics in one process, the bonding between the core and the reinforcement material is a mechanical one.

After impregnation of this three dimensional glass fabric also a chemical bonding is achieved. For glass fibre reinforced products this has all kinds of advantages, such as: a high impact resistance, a high delamination strength, a high stiffness and strength with low weight. The hollow structure can e.g. be used to run hot liquid through to heat up moulds or for integration of a leak detection system in a GRP-tank.

THREE DIMENSIONAL WOVEN GLASS FABRICS

A three dimensional woven glass fabric, as shown in figure 1, exists of two plain woven glass fabrics, which are simultaneously woven and connected by vertical glass fibres. Each plain woven fabric, in a standard three dimensional glass fabric, exists of 280 g/m² E-glass, equally spread in warp and weft direction. The weight of the vertical fibres depends on its height and density, which is in a standard three dimensional woven fabric about 500.000 vertical fibres per square meter.

Fig. 1 - Schematic view of a three dimensional woven glass fabric

In reality three dimensional woven glass fabrics consists of vertical fibres lined up in a row in weft direction, creating channels in between, as shown in figure 2. The channels with a width of 4 mm are visible in the warp cross-section. In the weft cross-section there are 2 vertical fibres per millimetre, almost building a wall. This three dimensional construction can rightly be called: "An integrated sandwich structure".

The standard program exists of 5 styles, only varying in thickness, as shown in table 1. On the velvet weaving machines the thickness can be varied from 2 to 10 mm and the weights between 500 and 1500 g/m².

2a

2b

Fig. 2 - Cross-sections of a three dimensional woven glass fabric style 86088, which is 6 mm thick: a) warp direction; b) weft direction.

Table 1. Standard program of formable three dimensional woven glass fabrics.

Thickness (mm)	Fabric Type	Weight (g/m ²)
3	86086	815
4½	86087	860
6	86088	910
8	86095	960
9½	86096	1035

POLYESTER PROPERTIES

The three dimensional woven glass fabric is used as a reinforcement material for polyester, vinylester, epoxy and phenolic matrices. In order to obtain an optimal laminate with polyester and vinylester matrices, it is important to know some typical aspects of this construction.

Table 2. Interaction between a three dimensional woven glass fabric and a polyester or vinylester matrix.

Fabric feature	Effect	Solution
Thin layers	Low exotherm	Reactive system
Large surface area/ Hollow structure	Oxygen inhibition/ Styrene evaporation	Surface cover additive (LSE)

A single three dimensional laminate produced with a conventional resin and curing system usually takes more than four hours. This is mainly caused by the very good heat-release of the three dimensional laminate structure. This results in a low exotherm, which is developed during the curing process. In a chemical reaction such as this polymerisation, the velocity is exponential related to the temperature. Of course all kinds of circumstances, such as additional reinforcement layers, exposure to the sun, etc., will accelerate the curing of the three dimensional laminate by an increase of the laminate temperature.

To improve the curing process of this resin, a surface covering additive can be added. This can be a pure paraffine wax, which results in a non adhesive laminate surface, or Byk S-740, which will maintain an adhesive surface after curing.

In principle every polyester or vinylester can be adapted to give an appropriate potlife and curing velocity, with respect to the three dimensional construction. This must be done by inhibiting with paratertiaire butylcatechol for polyesters and 2,4 pentanedione (=acetylaceton) for vinylesters each between 0.2 to 0.3 %WT. This will increase the potlife tremendously and will enable to increase the accelerator concentration, without having short potlife problems. The higher accelerator concentration will result in a higher exotherm and so the high heat-release of the three dimensional construction will be compensated. While looking for the right accelerator concentration always make sure that the peroxide concentration is between 1.5 and 2.5 %WT. The three dimensional construction is an open construction and oxygen inhibition can easily occur. This inhibition reaction also consumes a part of the peroxides present in the resin. If the peroxide concentration is less than 1.5 %WT, not enough peroxide will remain behind to completely cure the laminate properly. Increasing the accelerator concentration, which usually is cobalt naphthenate, is also

favourable because of its ability to capture oxygen from the air, before the oxygen will inhibit the curing system.

When optimising a resin cure system the peroxide choice should be paid attention to. For all polyester types very good results are obtained with acetylacetonperoxide (AAP) instead of methylethylketonperoxide (MEKP). The potlife is hardly changed, but the curing time decreases by 30 to 50 %, without any problems on high exotherm. Vinylester resins show very good results with cumene hydroperoxide (CHP = Trigonox 239A or Trigonox 239).

APPLICATION

The three dimensional woven glass fabric can be applied in a resin spray-up, hand lay-up, and pre-impregnation process. Working with the material must be done as follows: a) cut with scissors or an electrical trimming knife, b) fabric lay-up on dry or wet surface, c) all resin can be applied on top, d) the resin amount must be 1,5 times the fabric weight, e) in order to make a good contact to the mould the fabric should be rolled thoroughly, f) working with these fabrics can be learned quickly, g) the resin amount can visually be checked by the resin bridges building up in the pile-rows, h) On top of the fabric additional reinforcements can be laminated wet in wet unto 2 kg/m².

Parabeam 3D fabrics have proved their successful application in a wide range of products, e.g.: a) building industry for its low weight and thermal isolation properties, b) automotive industry for its low weight and high impact resistance, c) storage tanks as a leak detection room and its flexural stiffness, d) ultralight aircrafts for its low weight and delamination strength.

LAMINATE PROPERTIES

Three dimensional fabric laminates are not often used without additional reinforcements. On this basis it must be

compared with conventional constructions. For this reason Parabeam offers its customers calculation facilities, to calculate an alternative construction with a three dimensional fabric laminate. For some basic properties of the three dimensional laminate, the following tests have been carried out, as shown in table 3: a) compression tests in warp and weft direction parallel to the laminate surfaces, b) tensile tests in warp and weft direction parallel to the laminate surfaces, c) double lap shear tests in warp and weft direction parallel to the laminate surfaces, d) flatwise compression tests perpendicular to the laminate surface, e) four point long beam bending tests in warp and weft direction, f) four point short beam bending tests in warp and weft direction.

Table 3. Three dimensional laminate properties of style 86088 in weft direction with 60 %WT polyester resin and 40 %WT glass, without any extra reinforcement layers.

Test	Effect of	Strength MPa	Stiffness MPa
a	Faces	$\sigma(c) = 200$	$E(c) = 14000$
b	Faces	$\sigma(t) = 300$	$E(t) = 15000$
c	Core	$\tau = 1.6$	$G = 70$
d	Core	$\sigma(c) = 5.0$	--
e	Face	$\sigma(c) = 210$	$E \cdot I/W = 100N \cdot m$
f	Both	$\tau = 1.1$	--

With these properties and additional properties of other types reinforcement materials laminate calculations can be carried out. Four different constructions are compared in table 4: A) Parabeam 86087 and on each side 300 g/m² CSM, B) coremat 5mm and on each side 450 g/m² CSM, C) PVC-foam 60 kg/m³ 5mm and on each side 450 g/m² CSM, D) 6 layers of 450 g/m² CSM.

Table 4. Mechanical and physical comparison between four types of construction

		A	B	C	D
LAMINATE THICKNESS	mm	6.5	7.0	7.0	6.0
FLEXURAL RIGIDITY	N*m	140	135	130	130
BENDING STRENGTH	N	390	340	440	500
WEIGHT	kg/m ²	4.2	6.2	5.7	8.9

CONCLUSION

Parabeam 3D fabric enables GRP manufacturers to improve their products on several points, such as: a high bending stiffness and strength combined with a low weight, as a result of the integrated sandwich structure. Both the small amount of resin required and the fast impregnation caused by the capillary action of the vertical fibres, bring a cost price reduction. Three dimensional woven glass fabrics have a good formability, compared with other core materials. The hollow structure enables it to be used as a leak detection, cooling or heating room. Also because of the hollow structure the exotherm will be low and the product will not become warped after demoulding. It is an all glass laminate, which will give no temperature expansion problems, such as crack-damage. If necessary it can be recycled as a full glass/resin laminate. The fact that a thick laminate can be produced in one go, reduces the styrene evaporation.

Important: when working with polyester and vinylester resins, a proper curing system must be used.